

AFFIXATION IS THE MOST COMMON WAY TO FORM WORDS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article discusses about the major types of the word formation. It covers the types of word formation. Affixation-the most common way to form words.

Keywords: word formation, affixes, prefixes, suffixes.

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

АФФИКСАЦИЯ - НАИБОЛЕЕ РАСПРОСТРАНЕННЫЙ СПОСОБ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ СЛОВ НА АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

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Abstract: В данной статье рассматриваются основные типы словообразования. Он охватывает типы словообразования. Аффиксация - самый распространенный способ образования слов.

Keywords: словообразование, аффиксы, префиксы, суффиксальная.

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AFFIKSATSIYA - BU INGLIZ TILIDA SO'ZLARNI YASASHNING ENG KENG TARQALGAN USULI

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Abstract: Ushbu maqolada so'z yasalishining asosiy turlari haqida so'z boradi. U so'z yasalish turlarini qamrab oladi. Affiksatsiya - so'zlarni shakllantirishning eng keng tarqalgan usuli.

Keywords: so'z yasalishi, affikslar, old qo'shimchalar

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Word formation¹ is a process by which new words are created from existing words in a language. It can involve different factors, including the number and type of morphemes, the rules governing word order, and the meaning of the words. This paper focuses on the more minor types of word formation. Word formation as a source of enrichment of active and passive vocabulary.

The vocabulary of the modern English language² is replenished due to the formation of new words with the help of word-formation processes. In English, it is not uncommon for words belonging to one part of speech to form words belonging to some other part of speech. Most often this happens by affixing, that is, adding suffixes or prefixes. The affixation method is perhaps the most common traditional way of forming new words from existing ones.

Affixation³ is recognized by linguists as one of the most "fertile" methods of creating/forming new lexical units by combining stems of various types (word roots) with word-building affixes. It is also necessary to define the concept of fertility, or the so-called productivity, which is defined by the term "word-building activity", which means the ability of word-building means, that is, affixes, to participate in the formation of new lexical units.

The material for the implementation of this course work plan was 383 lexical units, which were formed by affixation and were selected from the additions to the Great Oxford Dictionary for the period from 2015 to 2018 and published on the main dictionary website (public.oed.com). Despite the fact that affixation has been studied and is still being studied by many linguists, due to the productivity of this method of word formation, the affix method needs to be further studied in more depth.

As a result of the analysis, it was found that out of 1420 words⁴ published in updates to the Oxford Dictionary, 383 were formed by affixation, of which 133 words were formed by prefixing and 250 by suffixes⁵. It is important to emphasize that in this analysis we did not take into account cases where such prefixes as aqua-, auto- were used, because they were considered as semi-affixes, that is, they can independently carry a semantic load and can exist as independent units.

Among other things, in 2015, out of 392 new units, 69 words formed using suffixation and 6 lexical units formed using prefixation were recorded.

In 2016, 66 lexical units formed by suffixation and 18 prefix neologisms were recorded. In total, 424 lexical units were recorded in the additions.

¹ Marchand H. The categories and types of present-day English word-formation – Wiesbaden: 1960.

² English Thesaurus Dictionaries: Oxford, Cambridge and Collins Co build dictionaries. 2011.

³ Henry Sweet. New English grammar, Stevenson, 1988.

⁴ Marchand H. The categories and types of present-day English word-formation – Wiesbaden: 1960.

⁵ Marchand H. The categories and types of present-day English word-formation – Wiesbaden: 1960.

Based on the information obtained during the study of this issue, it can be concluded that the interaction of morphemes⁶ of different etymologies in the formation of a word at the present stage of development of the English language occurs very freely. From this follows a high degree of assimilation of the overwhelming majority of affixes and root morphemes that take part in the process of word formation by means of affixation.

After analyzing the units obtained by affixing, we found that they can be conditionally divided as follows according to the area of use:

1. Science and medicine (eg allinase, archistriatal).
2. Business and business communication (eg skiving, designee).
3. Internet (online games) (eg firsting, Demogorgonian).

Let's talk a little specifically about suffixation: in modern English⁷, suffixation is a fairly viable and productive process of word formation.

To establish the meaning of a newly formed derivative word⁸, it is necessary to know what meaning the suffixes carry and what they contribute to the meaning of the lexical meaning of the derived word. The suffix is able to modify the meaning of the root (base) and predetermine the belonging of the derivative to one or another part of speech. It should be noted that suffixes are especially numerous among nouns and effectively take root with such general meanings as doer, tool, place of action, abstract names and words. We can give an example⁹ of the most common of them: for example, the actor suffixes -er/-ar/-or (teacher, registrar, actor), -ian (technician), -(i)st (mechanist), -ant/-ent (declarant , student), tool suffixes -er (roller), scene -tory (observatory), -age (harborage), etc

In linguistics¹⁰ if you see long words, you just need to break them down into their individual parts: the root, the prefixes, the suffixes, and sometimes individual words. The study of word formation involves learning about the structure of the target language, improving skills in finding information, developing literacy skills, and applying them in various aspects of everyday life. In addition, this research contributes to the study of the language at a higher level.

REFERENCES:

1. Алтаева А.Ш. Сложные слова в современном русском языке: Морфемная система и словообразовательная структура: Автореф. дисс. ... канд. филол. наук. – Алматы, 2004.

⁶ Алтаева А.Ш. Сложные слова в современном русском языке: Морфемная система и словообразовательная структура: Автореф. дисс. ... канд. филол. наук. – Алматы, 2004.

⁷ <http://www.wikipedia.org>.

⁸ Adams. A brief synchronic account of English word formation process.2001

⁹ <http://www.dissertation.com>

¹⁰ Елисеева В.В. Лексикология английского языка: учебник / В.В. Елисеева. — СПб.: СПбГУ, 2003.

2. Бортничук Е.Н. Словообразование в современном английском языке. – Киев: Высш. шк., 1988.
3. Елисеева В.В. Лексикология английского языка: учебник / В.В. Елисеева. – СПб.: СПбГУ, 2003.
4. Adams. A brief synchronic account of English word formation process. 2001
5. English Thesaurus Dictionaries: Oxford, Cambridge and Collins Co build dictionaries. 2011.
6. Marchand H. The categories and types of present-day English word-formation – Wiesbaden: 1960.
7. New Oxford Dictionary of English. Oxford University Press Inc., – N.Y., 1998, 2001.
8. Henry Sweet. New English grammar, Stevenson, 1988.

INTERNET SYTES:

9. [http: // www. wikipedia.org](http://www.wikipedia.org).
10. [http: // www. dissertation.com](http://www.dissertation.com)